

VARIATION OF THE DISCHARGE CURRENT AND JOSHI EFFECT WITH TIME IN IODINE VAPOUR UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE

BY G. S. DESHMUKH

The time variation in the conductivity i and the associated Joshi effect Δi has been observed over a temperature range of 30° to 90° in iodine vapour, aged under silent discharge at 0.5 kV of 500 cycles frequency. i and Δi show an initial increase followed by a periodic and synchronous self-reversal. The amplitude of this reversal increases with temperature but is damped when the system is preheated for a given time period. The conductivity decreases by 10 to 20% during the rest period varied from 30 to 720 minutes. Prolonged 'ageing' enhances and stabilises i , reduced and rendered unsteady due to its discontinuation. The periodic reversal of i and its diminution immediately after the rest period is not marked during ageing of bromine vapour. This is attributed, in part, to the dependence of i and Δi on the behaviour of the adsorption-like boundary layer formed as a result of the interaction between the electrode (glass) walls and the excited vapour. A capacitive change occurs due to the variation in the density or/and the dielectric constant of the adsorbed phase. This, as also the characteristic 'work function' of the boundary layer and its stability with and without the applied field determines the magnitude of i and Δi . A progressive recovery in the conductivity of bromine vapour with the duration of the rest period is associated with the marked instability of the adsorption layer of sodium bromide as suggested by its gradual sintering at room temperature and its abrogation due to adsorption of iodine. The results are in accord with Joshi's theory of the surface origin of the 'periodic effect' and the Δi phenomenon and suggest that sintering of the electrode layer is an additional determinant of the conductivity and the Joshi effect.

Earlier results reported the marked influence of 'ageing' *i. e.* a time variation at a constant applied potential V in the conductivity i , on the magnitude of the Joshi effect, an instantaneous and reversible photo-variation Δi in excited chlorine (Deo, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 76; Mallikarjunappa, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 197) and bromine (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1948, 14, 157). Extension of these observations to iodine vapour was suggested by the non-identity of the rising and falling V - i characteristics observed during studies of the potential variation of Δi in the above system (Deshmukh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 29A, 243). The present communication reports results for the synchronous and periodic reversal of i and Δi in excited iodine due to 'ageing' and its marked dependence on temperature, nature of the electrode surface and the duration of 'rest period' (*vide infra*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The general apparatus and the electrical circuit used were essentially similar as adopted previously (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *loc. cit.*). The occurrence of ageing *i. e.* a time variation of the conductivity in dark (i_0) of iodine vapour was studied at a series of temperatures in Siemens' type (glass) ozonisers, excited at various (fixed) applied potentials V of a given supply frequency. Iodine vapour was obtained from a glass bulb containing pure solid iodine. This was sealed serially through a capillary to the

annular space of the ozoniser. The entire system was evacuated on the tópler and the ozoniser was sealed off when it maintained a satisfactory vacuum. The ozoniser and the attached bulb were enclosed in an asbestos chamber, heated electrically. The quantity of iodine in the bulb was such that even at the highest temperature employed in this series of experiments some solid phase remained. The current i was measured with a double wave, oxide rectifier type, Cambridge A. C. microammeter. The current-time curves in Fig. 1 represent only one typical set of observations obtained at 30°, 80° and 90°.

The time variation of i_D after 'preheating' the system at a given temperature was studied. The data for 'ageing' obtained without preheating are termed as normal. A representative group of results observed at 0.5 kV with and without preheating the system for 360 minutes at 80° and 90° is shown in Fig. 1.

The influence of 'rest period', i.e. the interval between two successive exposures to discharge, on the variation of the discharge current i after 'ageing' was also studied. Iodine vapour excited at a constant applied V was allowed to age under the discharge under normal condition and also after preheating the system at a series of temperatures for a given time period. The discharge was discontinued when the current reached a stationary stage due to ageing and was restarted at the original potential after different durations for the 'rest period' as defined above. Fig. 2 illustrates a typical set of results observed at 90° by varying the rest period from 30 to 720 minutes during the ageing of iodine vapour at 0.5 kV.

TABLE I

'Ageing' influence on conductivity in dark and light and on the Joshi effect.

Current indicator = Oxide rectifier type A. C. microammeter. Frequency of the A. C. supply = 500 cycles/sec. Applied potential = 0.5 kV.

Time.	Temperature=45°.				Temperature=80°.			
	i_D .	i_L .	Δi .	% Δi .	i_D .	i_L .	Δi .	% Δi .
0 min.	40.0	39.0	1.0	2.5	50.5	47.5	3.0	5.9
10	42.0	41.0	1.0	2.3	53.5	50.5	3.0	5.6
20	46.5	45.5	1.0	2.1	62.0	58.5	3.5	5.6
30	48.5	47.5	1.0	2.0	81.0	78.0	3.0	3.7
40	51.0	50.0	1.0	1.9	86.5	84.5	2.5	2.9
50	53.0	52.0	1.0	1.8	91.0	89.5	2.5	2.7
60	57.0	56.0	1.0	1.7	88.0	85.5	2.5	2.8
70	47.0	46.0	1.0	2.1	76.0	73.5	2.5	3.2
80	38.5	37.5	1.0	2.8	65.0	63.0	2.0	3.0
90	35.0	34.0	1.0	2.9	60.0	58.0	2.0	3.3

The time variation of the associated Joshi effect, an instantaneous and reversible photo-variation Δi of the discharge current i , in iodine vapour was observed at a series

of temperatures under *normal* condition by allowing the system to age under the discharge at a constant exciting potential V .

The source of irradiation consisted of two 220 volt—200 Watt incandescent (glass) bulbs. The discharge current in dark (i_d) and that under irradiation (i_l) were measured at different time intervals during ageing. From this the net Joshi effect ($i_d - i_l = \Delta i$) and its corresponding relative value ($100 \Delta i / i_d = \% \Delta i$) were calculated. Data in Table I (*cf.* Fig. 3) refer to only one group of results obtained by exciting iodine vapour at 0.5 kV for 90 minutes at 45° and 80°.

DISCUSSION

The generality of the results, of which the data in Fig. 1 are but typical, suggests the following :

(a) an increase in the conductivity of iodine vapour during the initial stage ; (b) its increase ; (c) a periodic reversal of i followed by (d) the attainment of a constant stage. Thus e.g., at 80° under normal condition, the initial value of i in iodine vapour excited at 0.5 kV was 50.0 μ A. This increased due to ageing to a maximum of 92.0 μ A *i. e.* by about 80% in 60 minutes, and then decreased to 64.0 μ A (by 30%) in about 120 minutes. A further prolongation of ageing developed one more reversal of i of, however, a smaller amplitude till after about 210 minutes of continuous exposure to discharge, i reached a stationary stage corresponding to 56.0 μ A (*cf.* curve A, Fig. 1). In the other series of observations in which the system was preheated prior to the exposure to discharge for 360 minutes at 80°, i was initially 62.0 μ A. It increased to

FIG. 1

78.0 μ A (*i. e.* by about 25%) in 90 minutes and after 180 minutes of ageing it decreased to 72.0 μ A (*i. e.* by 7%). On further continuation of ageing for 240 minutes, the current increased by about 5% to a constant maximum value *viz.*, 76.0 μ A (*cf.* curve A', Fig. 1).

Results for 'ageing' at 90° with and without 'preheating' the system were on the whole similar to those mentioned above except that the amplitudes of current reversals were more pronounced and the initial and final values of *i* were larger by about 20% than those obtained at 80° (*cf.* curves B and B', Fig. 1). The time variation of *i* at 30° was much less pronounced and tended to the stationary stage after about 100 minutes of ageing under the discharge (*cf.* inset curve in Fig. 1). Compared with earlier results obtained in the case of bromine vapour (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *loc. cit.*) excited under silent discharge under conditions similar to those maintained in the present investigation, it would appear that changes (b) and (d) are essentially common in the time variation of *i* in bromine and iodine. It is suggested that the observed decrease in the conductivity *i* and the attainment of the stationary stage may be due to the formation and stabilisation under the discharge of an adsorption layer of iodine on the electrode (glass) walls, as postulated earlier in the case of bromine. It is, however, remarkable that the diminution in the conductivity of iodine vapour is preceded by a rapid increase of *i* during the initial stage of ageing. Furthermore, the current *i* does not reach the steady stage after its progressive diminution. The attainment of the stage (d) occurs through (c) *i. e.* a periodic reversal of *i*. The occurrence of (a) and (c) during the time variation of *i* in iodine vapour constitutes therefore a feature not observed in excited bromine. This alternating rise and fall in the conductivity, produced despite the constancy of the exciting conditions, is not consistent with the mechanism of reactions restricted to a homogeneous vapour phase. It is therefore suggested that this periodic time variation of *i* in iodine vapour may be due to the occurrence of a complex heterogeneous reaction involving different phases with a characteristic time rate for their formation and break-up under the discharge.

At a given temperature the vapour pressure of iodine is much smaller than that of bromine. The condensibility of iodine vapour should therefore be more than that of bromine. It may be assumed that a surface layer of condensed iodine is formed primarily on the walls of the discharge tube. A partial desorption of this layer due to ionic bombardment during the initial stage of ageing, under the discharge, may lead to an increase in the concentration of the excited vapour phase and therefore to a corresponding rise in the conductivity, *i*.

The initial increase of *i* to a maximum and its diminution during ageing may also be attributed to the dissociation under the discharge of iodine vapour and its subsequent adsorption on the walls of the discharge tube. Thompson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1887, 42A, 343) observed an appreciable and almost permanent increase of pressure during the exposure of iodine vapour to electric discharge. This he attributed to its dissociation under the discharge.

According to Joshi's equation (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) the discharge current *i* in an ozoniser circuit should increase with the increase in any one or more of the quantities,

the conduction current i/R_g , the total wall capacity C_w , and the capacity associated with the gas phase C_g . Under the operative conditions adopted in the present investigation, the mass of iodine vapour (and therefore the corresponding pressure and the threshold potential, V_m) should increase with temperature and may not contribute to a rise in i/R_g . The gas capacity, C_g , should vary synchronously with the pressure p ; an increase of i with p may therefore be anticipated.

Furthermore, it is known that the conductivity of glass is affected markedly with temperature. Manning (*Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1940, 12, 215) found that the conductivity of solid dielectrics increases with temperature and that a rapid rise in i suggests an incipient dielectric breakdown. This has been further illustrated by the observations of Hippel and Maurer (*Phys. Rev.*, 1941, 59, 820) on the temperature variation of the breakdown potential of silica in the crystalline and amorphous (glass) forms. Their results show that the breakdown strength (potential) of amorphous substances like glass decreases with temperature. Presumably, the breakdown potential is identifiable or related simply to the threshold potential, V_m . At a given V the current i depends on $V - V_m$ (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; 1946, 15, 281). The increase in i , observed at a constant V , may therefore be attributed to the decrease in the breakdown potential of the system with temperature.

The time variation of i may result from a corresponding change in C_w , the total wall capacity of the system, due to adsorption of iodine and the formation of adsorption complexes on the walls of the discharge tube. During exhaustive work on the dependence of adsorption on the applied potential V , Bluh (*Z. Physik*, 1931, 107, 56, 369) found that adsorption increased if the applied V exceeded a critical value. It may be suggested that ageing of the system, under the discharge, at a constant V also facilitates the process of adsorption and that the extent of adsorption may increase with the duration of ageing. It is known that the melting point of the adsorbate is lower than that of the bulk substance. Demougin (*Compt. rend.*, 1935, 200, 662) studied the saturation adsorption of iodine on various charcoals and on silica gel at temperatures above and below the melting point of iodine and showed that the amounts adsorbed were the same at 128°, 100° 60° and 17°. Remarkably enough, the ratio of the weights of iodine to the weight of ether adsorbed at saturation varied only from 5.0 to 5.3 for each of the seven adsorbents used. The ratio of the densities of liquid iodine and ether is 5.4, whereas that of solid iodine and liquid ether is 6.7. The adsorbed iodine simulated the liquid stage even 97 degrees below the normal melting point. Patrick and Land (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 1201) found no evidence of a melting point down to 70° *i. e.* even 44 degrees below the bulk melting point. This suggests that the primary adsorption layer of iodine formed during the initial stage of ageing is in the form of a surface film of semi-liquid iodine. This may react under the discharge with the glass walls of the discharge tube and lead to the formation of adsorption complexes with sodium iodide or/and iodate. Luedeking (*Chem. News*, 1890, 61, 1) observed that the (glass) walls of the discharge tube were chiefly responsible for the absorption of iodine vapour sparked between platinum electrodes. He attributed the adsorption to the formation of sodium iodide or/and iodate.

From Maxwell's relation $\mu^2 = K$, data (Hodgman, "Handbook of Chemistry & Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., 28th Edition, 1944, pp. 2138, 2141, 2145) for the refractive index of glass, iodine and sodium iodide (μ being 1.6, 3.36 and 1.77 respectively) show that the dielectric constant of iodine and sodium iodide is greater than that of glass. Since the effective wall capacity C_w increases with K , the adsorption of iodine and the formation of sodium iodide on the walls of the discharge tube should contribute to a rise in the conductivity, i .

Goetz (*Phys. Rev.*, 1929, 38, 373) observed that the thermionic work function of the metals Cu, Ag and Au changed sharply in passing through the melting point and that the work function is larger for the phase of greater density i.e. of smaller atomic separation. Since μ for the glass, bromine and sodium bromide is about 1.6, the dielectric constant K and the corresponding wall capacity C_w should not change appreciably due to the adsorption of bromine and the formation of sodium bromide due to ageing. The density of sodium bromide is, however, greater than that of condensed bromine (Hodgman, *loc. cit.*, pp. 357, 456). A surface film of NaBr, formed during ageing under the discharge, would increase the work function at the boundary layer. The decrease in the conductivity i , observed in excited bromine (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *loc. cit.*), should therefore follow. On the other hand, the density of liquid iodine and NaI is less than that of solid iodine (Hodgman, *loc. cit.*, pp. 392, 460); the formation of an adsorption layer of semi-liquid iodine or/and NaI under the discharge may reduce the work function at the electrode surface and lead to the observed increase in i . The conductivity may increase to a maximum till the electrode surface (s) is covered completely with the primary adsorption layer of iodine or/and NaI. Further adsorption of iodine on the surface of the primary layer, during prolonged ageing of the system under the discharge, may decrease the work function and reduce i as observed. Baedekar (*Ann. Physik*, 1907, 22, 756; 1909, 29, 566) reported a marked increase in the conductivity of cuprous iodide mixed with an excess of iodine. This was not due to the internal adsorption of the electropositive atoms able to emit their valence electrons but to the taking up of an electronegative element. Tubandt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 110, 234) extended these observations to other cuprous halides and showed that their conductivity also increased by the adsorption of an excess of halogen. Other electronegative elements like sulphur and oxygen, when added to certain sulphides and oxides, enhanced the conductivity appreciably; the influence on the conductivity of cuprous oxide by the taking up of oxygen has been especially studied thoroughly by many investigators. According to Wagner (*Phys. Z.*, 1931, 32, 641) the excess electronegative element in the lattice forms excess negative ions so that just as many of the positive ions must carry a higher charge. Thus in the case of cuprous iodide, extra I^- ions are formed in the lattice and an equally large number of Cu^{++} ions. These are responsible for the electronic conduction. They are one electron short and capture an electron from a Cu^+ ion which in turn is transformed into a Cu^{++} ion characteristic of the 'defect conduction'. It is interesting to note, however, that with an increased concentration of electronegative element, the conductivity decreases at high temperatures. This has been observed in the case of CuI , Cu_2O and also in some semi-conductors like Ag_2O which are provided with an extra amount of electropositive element (Boer, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1935, 32, 106).

Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 16, 281) has emphasised the significance of the data for the time variation of i as a means of elucidating the course of a discharge reaction, especially when the determination of the change of gas pressure and a time to time analysis of the products of reaction are not feasible. He has attributed the time variation in the conductivity i to a change in the intensity of the field at the electrode surface or/and to the formation of the products of reaction of 'limited life'. According to him the surface activity of some of the reaction products may lead to the formation of an adsorption-like electrode layer. A capacitative change resulting from the formation of this layer would affect the conductivity i of the system. The periodic variation of i may be associated with an intermittent sorption and desorption of the above layer or/and the formation and decomposition under the discharge of unstable intermediate products of reaction at the surface. The production, at a constant applied V and temperature, of a spontaneous and long sustained 'periodic effect' during the decomposition of nitrogen dioxide (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75) and in the N_2O-H_2 (Joshi and Deshmukh, *Nature*, 1945, 155, 483) and $S-N_2$ (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, unpublished data) reactions under silent discharge are explicable with the above mechanism. On this view the reversal of i during the later part of 'ageing', indicative of a like variation in C_w and C_g , may be attributed to the partial desorption of the adsorbed layer of iodine or/and the surface decomposition of unstable adsorption complexes with NaI or/and $NaIO_3$. It may be emphasised that a sensibly large rise in the conductivity has been observed in these laboratories during the decomposition, under the discharge, of an annular film of KI_3 in vacuum.

The attainment of the stationary stage in the conductivity may be envisaged as the stabilisation of the adsorption layer under the influence of the applied fields. It is very likely that the dissociation of iodine vapour and the conductivity of glass are enhanced as a result of preheating the system at high temperatures. This preheating is not favourable to the formation of a stable adsorption layer. The value of i is therefore large, but the amplitudes of current fluctuations are comparatively much less pronounced than those observed under normal conditions.

The thermal effects, mentioned above, leading to the increase of i in a solid phase are low at ordinary temperature. For this reason, and also since the vapour pressure of iodine is but small (0.47 mm.) at 30° , the smaller value of i , as observed, follows. The comparatively even character of the corresponding current—time curve (cf. inset curve in Fig. 1) may therefore be associated with the greater stability of the adsorption layer due to moderately low temperature.

Fig. 2 shows the influence of 'rest period' of different durations on the variation of i in iodine vapour, aged under the discharge at 0.5 kV with and without preheating the system at 90° .

It is seen that under normal conditions i reaches the stationary stage of $50.0\mu A$ in about 210 minutes and remains sensibly steady on further prolongation of ageing for 330 minutes. The discharge was discontinued at this stage and was restarted after a rest period of 30 minutes. It is interesting to note that after the rest period the

current was unsteady and reached the stationary stage on the continuation of ageing for about 60 minutes. A series of successive rest periods of 40, 180, 240 and 720

FIG. 2

minutes' duration were employed after i was stabilised previously due to ageing. It is significant to observe that as a result of discontinuation of the discharge during the rest period the discharge current decreases by about 10 to 20% and tends to a steady stage only after prolonged ageing. The results obtained after preheating the system at 90° for 300 minutes and employing different durations of rest period are similar to those mentioned above; the amplitude of current variation is, however, less pronounced and i is larger by about 40% than that observed under normal condition (cf. Fig. 2).

It is suggested that the stabilisation of the adsorption layer due to the adsorption-desorption equilibrium, produced under prolonged ageing of the system under the discharge, leads to the stage of steady conductance. In the absence of the electrical field (*i.e.* during the rest period) this equilibrium is shifted so as to favour adsorption; this may reduce the conductivity i as observed. A partial desorption of the adsorption layer due to the ionic bombardment after the rest period should reduce the work function at the boundary layer and increase p , C_a and C_p . A corresponding rise in i should therefore follow.

Earlier results in the case of bromine vapour (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *loc. cit.*) showed that i increased partially or fully to its initial value after a given rest period. This was ascribed, in part, to the desorption of the adsorbed vapour. It is instructive to consider the influence of external factors, especially temperature, on the behaviour of surface films. The nature of the surface of the adsorbant is altered by heating. The process of increasing the surface is called activation, that of decreasing it by heat

is termed as 'sintering'. 'Every adsorbent sinters if heated to high enough temperatures' (Brunauer, "Physical Adsorption of Gases and Vapours", Oxford, 1943, p. 357). This is attributed to the growth of the particle size due either to changes in the physical or chemical nature of the surface. Boer and Dippel, (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **B21**, 198) observed the marked suitability of thin transparent films of inorganic salts, obtained by sublimation in a high vacuum, for the study of the absorption of light by matter in the adsorbed state. The adsorption of iodine on one of these salt films (e. g. calcium fluoride) gives only a monomolecular covering. The fact that the colour of adsorbed iodine can still be seen is due to the laminary structure of the salt film whereby many monomolecular layers of adsorbed iodine lie one behind the other in the path of light (Boer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B16**, 300). By heating at temperatures between 150° and 350° a decrease in the surface of the salt film takes place due to sintering. During the process the film remains clear; the laminae merely become firmly attached to each other so that the interlaminary surface is considerably decreased and a number of active spots disappears. In the adsorption of iodine the amount adsorbed is very much decreased and the number of active spots that have disappeared is large compared to the decrease in the total surface. The forces which hold the surfaces of the laminae together after sintering are considerably weaker than those which act within the salt lattice. Molecules and atoms which are especially strongly adsorbed abrogate the effect of sintering. Thus the film of calcium fluoride sintered at temperatures not higher than 350° is completely broken up by the adsorption of caesium and the original value of the adsorption of iodine can be measured (Boer and Dippel, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1933, **30**, 78, 221).

Compared with the films of calcium or barium halides, the layers of alkali halides are more easily sintered. A film of sodium bromide sinters gradually even at ordinary room temperature. In this case the opening of the film is also easier; the adsorption of iodine leads to the opening of the sintered film of NaBr (Boer, "Electron Emission and Adsorption Phenomena", Cambridge, 1935, p. 188). The initial decrease in the conductivity i of excited bromine has been attributed to the adsorption of bromine vapour on the walls of the discharge tube. It is likely that a surface film of sodium bromide is formed under the discharge due to the interaction of the adsorbed vapour and the electrode (glass) walls. A gradual sintering of this layer during the rest period may lead to a rise in the concentration of the active vapour phase and therefore to a corresponding increase in the % restoration of i with the duration of the rest period. The decrease of i , as observed in the present investigation, after each successive rest period, suggests that unlike bromine or/and NaBr the adsorption layer of iodine and NaI, formed during ageing of iodine vapour under the discharge, is comparatively stable. The relative stability of NaBr and NaI, as judged by the data for their thermal decomposition, however, shows that the former is more stable than the latter. That, this perhaps may not be the only criterion for determining the stability of the compounds, especially in the adsorbed state, is suggested by the observation that the adsorbed film of NaBr sinters even at the ordinary room temperature. Furthermore, the abrogation of the sintered layer of NaBr by the adsorption of iodine

supports the assumption that the surface film of NaI may be more stable than that of NaBr.

In the absence of the exciting field the adsorption layer of iodine or/and NaI may catalyse the recombination of the iodine atoms and lead to an increase in the threshold potential, V_m or/and decrease C_m , the effective capacity of the annular walls. This may reduce the conductivity i due to the rest period.

According to Joshi's theory (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26) an adsorption like boundary layer, formed from the wall adsorption of the ions and molecules of the excited gas, is the chief seat of Δi . Photoelectrons emitted from this layer due to external irradiation are captured by the excited gas particles to give slow moving negative ions and produce the photodiminution Δi as a space charge effect. Since the probability of electron capture by a particle depends on P/E , where P is the pressure and E , the electrical field, the favourable effect of P at constant E on the magnitude of Δi follows. Results in Table I (cf. Fig. 3) show that the discharge current in the dark (i_d) increases initially, reaches a maximum and then decreases as a result of ageing the system under the discharge at 0.5 kV. The curve for i_d in Fig. 3 does not, however, represent the time variation of i under light. The points

on the line denote the values obtained for i when the system is irradiated for 30 seconds at different intervals during ageing. The net Joshi effect Δi is sensibly constant at low temperatures but varies periodically and synchronously with i at comparatively high temperatures. Thus e. g., at 80° and 0.5 kV, i increased by 15% in 15 minutes of exposure to discharge and decreased by about 45% on further continuation of ageing for 90 minutes (cf. Table I). The relative effect, $\% \Delta i$, decreased initially to a minimum and increased again when i and Δi were decreasing. The initial increase

of i has been attributed, in part, to the desorption of iodine vapour adsorbed primarily on the walls of the discharge tube. Since p , and therefore C_g , increases during desorption, a corresponding rise in i and Δi should ensue. The variation in p is less pronounced at low temperatures due to the greater stability of the adsorption layer. The net Joshi effect Δi is therefore sensibly constant at 45° (cf. Table I and Fig. 3). The above suggestion can only be a partial explanation since the variation in i and Δi is far larger than the corresponding changes in p and C_g due to desorption. Previous results in the case of chlorine (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 343) showed that, within limits, the relative Joshi effect $\% \Delta i$ increases from a low value to almost 93% current diminution under light with p . It is also remarkable that a practically 100% Joshi effect occurs in Hg vapours excited under topler vacuum (0.001138 mm. Hg). Similarly the Joshi effect, as large as 60% to 70%, has been observed in sulphur and selenium vapour (vapour pressure being 0.0003 and 0.0008 mm. at 49° and 193° respectively). This suggests that compared with changes in p , the nature and behaviour of the adsorption-like boundary layer is a more important determinant of the magnitude of Δi . The formation of the primary adsorption layer of iodine or/and NaI and the resultant change in the density of the adsorbed phase may reduce the work function at the boundary layer. The total wall capacity, C_w , and therefore i and Δi should increase as a consequence. The increased adsorption of iodine and the growth of secondary adsorption layers due to the prolonged ageing should reduce p , C_g , C_w and increase the work function at the electrode surface. This may lead to a corresponding reduction in i and Δi as observed. Studies of the potential reversibility of the Joshi effect, Δi , in iodine vapour (Deshmukh, *loc. cit.*) have shown that its magnitude and even sign is affected by but a small change in the applied V, and that the production of the positive Joshi effect $+\Delta i$ is favoured by high temperature and low applied potential. In the present series of experiments, the negative Joshi effect $-\Delta i$ has been observed in iodine vapour excited at 0.5 kV at 90° . It may be assumed that excitation of the system at the above potential facilitates the formation of slow moving negative ions and masks the positive effect $+\Delta i$.

In conclusion, the author wishes to express his grateful thanks to Prof. S. S. Joshi for his keen interest and valuable guidance during the work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARES.

Received November 13, 1948.